

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF EXERCISE MOTIVATION BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE UNDER 17 YEARS SOCCER PLAYERS

Arif Mohammad¹ⁱ, Mohammad Ahsan²

¹Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Physical Education,
Department of Teacher Training and Non Formal Education (IASE),
Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India

²Ph.D., Assistant Professor (Biomechanics), Department of Physical Therapy,
College of Applied Medical Sciences,
University of Dammam, Dammam, Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

The purpose of the present research was to compare the level of exercise motivation of male and female soccer players. Secondary purpose of this work was to answer of the question “*which gender needs what extend of exercise motivation to perform better in sports?*” The method carried out in this study was quantitative in nature and based on the questionnaire study. Population of this research consisted on all male and female soccer players in Rakiraki Public High School, Kings Road, Fiji. Among the total population the sample consisted on 50 boys and 50 girls (all subjects were below 17 years of age). The Exercise Motivation Inventory developed by Markland and Hardy, (1993) was used to gauge the level of exercise motivation of both genders. Results of statistical analysis (t-test) showed that there was no significant difference between male and female players on their level of exercise motivation, but the mean value of female players was found considerably higher than the male players. This finding leads to conclude that both male and female under 17 years soccer players having same level of exercise motivation.

Keywords: exercise motivation, male soccer players, female soccer players

ⁱ Correspondence: email amohammad3@jmi.ac.in

1. Introduction

Understanding and enhancing motivation has long been a major concern in sport. Without motivation athletes would not desire to excel in their sport, coaches would no longer strive to unify the team, and a player's drive to set and reach goals would end (Ali, 2010; Ali, Hussain, & Rahaman, 2010). The biggest and most common reason that affects soccer performance is motivation or lack of it (Ahmadi, Namazizadeh, Abdoli, & Seyed, 2009). Generally, speaking motivation is guided by the hope of success and the fear of failure. When you lack the self-belief and confidence, there is a chance you also lack motivation (Atkinson, 1977; Munroe-Chandler, Krista, & Hall, 2005; Najah, & Rejeb, 2015). It is the force that initiates, guides and maintains goal-oriented behaviours (Shafizadeh, 2007; Ingledew, Markland, & Medley, 1998). It is what causes us to take action. The forces that lie beneath motivation can be biological, social, emotional or cognitive in nature (Hollembek, & Amorose, 2005).

Exercise motivation is an important concern due to the complex nature of the activity, the abundance of health benefits inherent in habitual exercise (Kavussanu, & McCauley, 1995). Sport psychologists are seeking for ways to keep athletes at a desirable level of motivation, to effectively control the aggravating and debilitating factors of this basic issue that can overshadow the technical and tactical performance of athletes, and to develop the efficiency of individual and group athletes in performing sport skills (Li, & Harmer, 1996). Athletes usually tend to forget the stresses of competitions or try to tolerate them (van Heerden, 2014). They work for long hours to perfect their skills and they subject their body and mind to maximum pressure (Khan, Khan, & Ahmad, 2010).

Accordingly, Khan, Khan, and Ahmad, (2010) various motivations exist in individuals for participation in sports exercises such as sense of relatedness and growth. Moreover, he showed that flawed leadership styles can decrease intrinsic motivation. An investigation conducted by Ahmadi, et al. (2009) who compared the motivation of professional, semi-professional, and amateur football players found that amateur players presented a higher level of a motivation in comparison with professional players and their sportive competence was at a lower level; nonetheless, they reported lower levels of identified regulation. On the other hand, professional and semi-professional athletes presented higher levels of interjected regulation and believed that their competence in football is due to learning and can be improved.

Motivation in athletes depends on their motivational forces (Amorose, & Horn, 2000). Studying motivation is an attempt to understand the reasons behind behaviours. Identifying the needs and developing the talents of athletes and making conclusions

from their own efforts and that of the athletes have made researchers in the area of sports psychology recognize the psychological issues and take notice of the issues related to motivation (Monazami, Hedayatikatooli, Neshati, Beiki, 2012). Thus, the point in this research is to identify the motivational factors in male and female soccer players.

Materials and Methods

Participants

There were a total of 100 participants in this study. The population of the research consisted of male and female team players in Rakiraki Public High School, Kings Rd, Fiji. Among the total population 50 boys and 50 girls were selected as sample for the study. The age of the subjects was between 15 to 17 years.

Measuring Instrument

The Exercise Motivation Inventory (EMI) developed by Markland and Hardy, (1993) was used to determine the motivational level of both the groups. The EMI was developed to measure motivation specifically in the sport context. The EMI was developed as a means of assessing participation motives in order to examine such issues as the influence of motives on exercise participation, how such motives might influence the choice of activities undertaken, how affective responses to exercising may be influenced by reasons for exercising and how involvement in physical activity might have a reciprocal influence on participation motives.

In particular, the authors developed the instrument to examine questions concerning the functional significance of exercise motives from the perspective of Deci and Ryan's (1985) self-determination theory.

Procedure of Data Collection

A total of 100 questionnaires were distributed (50 per gender) with all being returned back after completing. Two weeks allowed for returning the questionnaire. No questionnaires were received after that time.

The analysis of the questionnaires from all the participants was carried out. Each of the participant's questionnaires was analysed by individually calculating the scoring for all the questions and then the total scoring of each participant. This was done for all males and all females.

Results

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation and t value of exercise motivation between male and female players

	Means	SD	t value
Male	191.08	30.97	1.39
Female	200.48	36.25	

Tabulated $t_{0.05} = 1.98$

Above cited Table 1 indicated that the t-test score is 1.39 this t value determines that there is no significant difference between male and female players in exercise motivation. Though there is no significant difference between male and female players in exercise motivation, but the mean value of exercise motivation is considerably higher of female players than male players.

Figure 1: Mean comparison of exercise motivation between male and female

Discussion

The purpose of the present research was to compare the exercise motivation of male and female under 17 soccer players of Rakiraki Public High School. The findings of this work shows that feeling of joy and pleasure, sensing the advantages and valuable effects of sport, inner confidence, feeling the need for physical exercises, enjoying mental hygiene and reduction of mental stress, satisfaction of the desire for relatedness, weight loss and fitness were the most important exercise motivations for people to participate in soccer in school.

As the results of this research shows female players and the male players have a same level of exercise motivation which is not significant. Female soccer players scored higher on the mean than male soccer players. One explanation for the women's higher scores on the scoring may be due to the stereotype and/or belief that muscular women do not look feminine. Klein (1993) suggests that gender role conflict can occur in female athletes when women desire to build athletic body (muscle mass), but also want to remain attractive to men.

According to Butt's (1978) theory a tendency of one of the psychological components of motivation would predict dominance in one of the social components of motivation of either competition or cooperation. Since there were no significant differences between males and females in the exercise motivation scales, one cannot predict dominance at any social components of motivation with the subjects in this study. Thus it is proposed that future investigations should continue to explore gender differences in basic need satisfaction in order to gain a better understanding of the motivational processes underpinning sport activities.

Conclusions

The present research was an attempt to broaden our understanding of soccer players' exercise motivation. When comparing both male and female on exercise motivation, female soccer players and male players scored significantly the same on the scale. Hence no significant difference was found on the scale of exercise motivation.

In conclusion, investigating the exercise motivation of male and female soccer players is a necessary step in understanding this complex and popular sport. Measuring a construct such as exercise motivation in sport is a difficult task due to the endless number of variables in a player's personality. However, human nature dictates that similarities do exist among our personalities, which, if measured, can help us to predict our behaviour.

References

1. Ahmadi, S., Namazizadeh, M., Abdoli, B., & Seyed, A.A. (2009). The comparison of achievement motivation between soccer players of high and low ranking teams in super league of Iran. *Olympic Fall*, 3(47), 19-28.
2. Ali, J. (2010). A study of achievement motivation in relation to performance of badminton players. *Vyayam-Vidnyan*, 43(3), 41-44.

3. Ali, J. Hussain, I., & Rahaman, A. (2010). A comparative study of aggression and sports achievement motivation of hockey players of Manipur. *AMASS Multilateral Research Journal*, 2(2), 23-26.
4. Amorose, A. J., & Horn, T. S. (2000). Intrinsic motivation: Relationships with collegiate athletes' gender, scholarship status, and perceptions of their coaches' behavior. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 22, 63-84.
5. Atkinson, J.W. (1977). Motivation for achievement. In: T. Blass (Ed.), *Personality variables in social behavior*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum, 1, 144.
6. Butt, D.S. (1978). Short scales for the measurement of sport motivations. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 10, 203-216.
7. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York: Plenum.
8. Hollebeak, J., & Amorose, A. J. (2005). Perceived coaching behaviours and college athletes' intrinsic motivation: A test of Self-Determination Theory. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 17, 20-36.
9. Ingledew, D.K.I., Markland, D., & Medley, A. (1998). Exercise motives and stages of change. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 3, 477-489.
10. Kavussanu M., & McCauley, E. (1995). Exercise and optimism: are highly active individuals more optimistic? *Journal of Sport Exercise Psychology*, 17, 246-258.
11. Khan, Z., Khan, S., & Ahmad, N. (2010). Sports achievement motivation among Asian players: a study. *AMASS Multilateral Research Journal*, 2(2), 7-9.
12. Klein, A.M. (1993). *Little big men*. New York: State University of New York Press.
13. Li, F., & Harmer, P. (1996). Testing the simple assumption underlying the Sport Motivation Scale: A structural equation modeling analysis. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 67, 396-405.
14. Markland, D., & Hardy, L. (1993). The Exercise Motivations Inventory: Preliminary development and validity of a measure of individuals' reasons for participation in regular physical exercise. *Personality & Individual Differences*, 15, 289-296.
15. Monazami, M., Hedayatikatooli, A., Neshati, A., Beiki, Y. (2012). A comparison of the motivation of male and female competitive athletes in Golestan, Iran. *Annals of Biological Research*, 3(1), 31-35.
16. Munroe-Chandler, Krista, A., & Hall, C.R. (2005). Enhancing the collective efficacy of a soccer team through motivational general-mastery imagery. *Imagination Cognition and Personality* 24(1), 51-67.
17. Najah, A., & Rejeb, R. B. (2015). The psychological profile of youth male soccer players in different playing positions. *Advances in Physical Education*, 5, 161-169.

18. Shafizadeh, M. (2007). Relationship between goal orientation, motivational climate and perceived ability with intrinsic motivation and performance in physical education university students. *Journal of Applied Sciences*, 7(19), 2866-2870.
19. Van Heerden, C.H. (2014). Expressed motives of students for sport participation in a South African context. *Journal of Physical Education Research*, 1, 01-07.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).